

PREPARATION AND THERMOELECTRIC PROPERTY OF LAYERED NANO-COMPOSITE OXIDE

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1. Introduction

Recently, low dimensional nanostructured materials such as quantum dot superlattices [1] and Si nanowire [2] have been reported to enhance thermoelectric figures of merit. For oxide, it was reported that the superlattice structure of SrTiO₃/SrTi_{0.8}Nb_{0.2}O₃ exhibits a giant Seebeck coefficient due to quantum confinement effect. In the structure, the confinement of electrons within a unit cell layer thickness of SrTiO₃ was reported to enhance the Seebeck coefficient by a factor of ~5 compared to that of bulk at room temperature.

Koumoto et al. made an attempt to realize the quantum well structure of the bulk materials by exfoliating thermoelectric Na_{0.7}CoO₂. [3] The exfoliation, which modify the interlayer structure, of the layered cobalt oxide can give us an understanding of the relationship between the physical property and the structural dimensionality. Furthermore, the exfoliation and restacking of the layered cobalt oxide could provide an effective way to make a new multilayered nanostructure with controlled physical properties. In the present work, we attempted to exfoliate the sodium cobalt oxide into nano-layer with a thickness of several nanometers. Furthermore, the thermoelectric properties of the restacked cobalt oxide from the exfoliated nano-layer were evaluated.

2. Experimental

The exfoliated cobalt oxide was obtained through chemical oxidation and organic amine treatment of pristine, Na_{0.7}CoO₂. A polycrystalline sample of Na_{0.7}CoO₂ was synthesized by the standard solid state reaction. The oxidized Na_{0.35}CoO₂·yH₂O were prepared from the pristine by reacting with Na₂S₂O₈ solution. An excess amount of organic amines (butyl-, octyl-, dodecyl-, hexadecyl-amine) was

reacted with the oxidized sodium cobalt oxide to get the exfoliated cobalt oxide. The products were washed with DI water/ethanol, centrifuged, and dried at 80°C. Colloidal suspension of the exfoliated product was obtained by dispersing the powder. Restacked product was obtained by mixing the suspension with calcium chloride solution, and then separated by centrifugation. For thermoelectric measurement, the restacked powder was pressed by CIP and sintered at 900°C in air. Thermal diffusivity, α , was determined by a laser flash method (Netzsch Instruments Inc., Burlington, Massachusetts, USA). Specific heat capacity was measured by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC-60, Shimadzu). The thermal conductivity was calculated via the equation, $\kappa = \alpha\rho c_p$, where ρ is the density and c_p is the specific heat capacity of the material. For the Seebeck coefficient, the thermoelectromotive force was measured as a function of the temperature difference using commercial equipment (Ozawa Science, Thermoelectric Property Measurement System, model RZ2001i) on a bar-type sample. The electrical resistivity was measured with a dc four-probe technique using a rectangular bar with dimensions of 2 mm × 2 mm × 15 mm.

3. Results and Discussion

The parent compound of Na_{0.7}CoO₂ has a hexagonal layered structure consisting of the two-dimensional layers of CoO₂ and charge balancing Na⁺ ions. Similarly, the oxidized compounds of Na_{0.35}CoO₂·yH₂O consists of electronically active planes separated by swellable layers (Na/H₂O). [4] According to the content of the interlayer water, the monohydrate form (y = 0.6) and the bihydrate form (y = 1.3) exist. In this work, in order to effectively intercalate Na_{0.7}CoO₂ by organic amine molecules, the oxidized form was, at first, derived through chemical oxidation using persulfate solution. The

increased oxidation state and reduced layer charge density are favorable for the intercalation of amine molecules due to the weakened layer-by-layer interaction.

Fig. 1. TEM images for the exfoliated and restacked Na_xCoO_2 . (a) bright field image for the exfoliated sample by octylamine, (b) HREM image for the restacked sample after sintering.

Fig. 1 represents electron microscopic images of the exfoliated and restacked cobalt oxides. The exfoliated cobalt oxide exhibits a plate-shaped crystallite, which makes it difficult to observe the microstructure in the direction perpendicular to basal plane. Therefore, the colloidal suspension was dried in a polymer substrate and embedded in acrylic resin and then sliced by microtome to prepare the TEM sample. As shown in Fig. 1(a), the exfoliated sample exhibits thin nano-flakes with thicknesses of less than 100nm, in which very thin nanosheets are interleaved with thicknesses of ~ 10 nm.

Figs 2(a), 2(b), and 2(c) show the temperature dependence of the Seebeck coefficient, electrical conductivity, and thermal conductivity, respectively, of the pristine, the exfoliated, and the restacked cobalt oxides. Whereas the Seebeck coefficients of the exfoliated (octylamine-treated) and restacked samples are larger than that of the pristine, their electrical conductivities decrease after the exfoliation and the restacking process. The chemical oxidation seems to reduce the electrical conductivity of the exfoliated sample. The restacked sample exhibits a decrease in the electrical conductivity compared to the pristine, which might be due to the many possible defect at the interface between the exfoliated nano-layer or a change in carrier density. The thermal conductivity of the restacked sample exhibits a marked decrease compared to that of the pristine, which results from phonon scattering at the interface between the sodium cobalt oxide layers. As a result, ZT (figure of merit) value for the restacked

sample is about 0.6 at 800 °C, which is larger than that of the pristine.

Fig. 2. (a) Seebeck coefficient, (b) electrical conductivity, (c) thermal conductivity for the pristine (solid triangle), the exfoliated sample (gray triangle), the restacked (open rectangle) sample.

4. Conclusion

Thermoelectric oxide of $\text{Na}_{0.7}\text{CoO}_2$ was exfoliated into nanoplatelet of Na_xCoO_2 by soft chemical method. Thermoelectric properties of the nano-composite of sodium cobalt oxide by the restacking of the exfoliated nano-layer were evaluated.

5. References

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